

SecAwarenessTruss

D2.2 Report on Training and Cyber-range capabilities and requirements

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Due date:	31/05/2024		
Version number:	Final	Status:	Submitted

Project Number:	101128049	Project Acronym:	SecAwarenessTruss
Project Title:	A Dynamic Training programme based on Cyber-Ranges Leveraging IT Security, Privacy and Data Protection Culture and Awareness of Critical Information Infrastructures		
Start date:	January 1 st , 2024		
Duration:	36 months		
Call identifier:	DIGITAL-ECCC-2022-CYBER-03		
Topic:	DIGITAL-ECCC-2022-CYBER-03-CYBER-RESILIENCE		

Dissemination Level	
PU: Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SEN: Sensitive	<input type="checkbox"/>

Funded by the
European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101128049

Revision History

Revision	Date	Who	Description
0.1	23/02/2024	E. Floros (PAGNI), I. Petrakis (PAGNI)	ToC
0.2	29/04/2024	K. Magkos (MDG), M. Katsifarakis (PAGNI)	input to sections 3.2, 2.3, 4
0.3	02/05/2024	OUC (E. Stavrou)	Input to section 2.4
0.4	09/05/2024	A. Grigoriadis, G. Pouraimis (HMOD)	Input to section 3.1
0.5	13/05/2024	N. Nikoloudakis, D. Merkouris (PPC)	Input to section 2.2
0.6	14/5/2024	E. Floros (PAGNI), N. Nikoloudakis (PPC), OUC (E. Stavrou), A. Grigoriadis, G. Pouraimis (MDG), P. Mpepis (OTE)	Input to sections 4, 2.1
0.7	20/5/2024	E. Floros (PAGNI), I. Vasilaki (PAGNI)	Document format optimization, KPIs addition
0.8	31/5/2024	A. Grigoriadis, G. Pouraimis (HMOD) A. Andreoudi (MDG)	Internal Review
1.0	31/5/2024	E. Floros (PAGNI), N. Nikoloudakis (PPC)	Final consolidation

Disclaimer

This document has been produced in the context of the SecAwarenessTruss Project. This project is part of the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and is as such funded by the European Commission. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. All information in this document is provided 'as is' and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability with respect to this document, which is merely representing the authors' view.

Executive Summary

Abstract: This Deliverable focuses on collecting cyber security training requirements and identifying the training needs of different stakeholders (coming from the targeted critical sectors of telecom, energy, healthcare, and maritime) at national, regional, and European level. To achieve this, a systematic requirements elicitation approach will be established, having a two-fold focus: a) to identify the requirements and specific needs of the participating stakeholders, which represent different critical sectors and with different needs with regard to IT security; and b) to substantially engage the external stakeholders so as to gain feedback regarding their needs and priorities in the frame of the project, through the realization of interviews with their users expressing significant interest on the project's technologies and vision, and through the large-scale circulation of structured questionnaires, utilizing the dissemination channels of the participating partners. These requirements will be used for the customization of the Cyber Range Platform (T2.4 and WP4) and the establishment of the training programs and the specification of the training scenarios (WP3), which must demonstrate these requirements. This Deliverable will also include a preliminary analysis of Cyber-range training requirements imposed by the existing national and European legal and regulatory framework and regime (e.g. (NIS Directive and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)). The identification of relevant sets of legislation (e.g. regarding data protection, privacy and security) and ethical principles will lead to a high-level description of provisions which will need to be taken into account in the course of the project and the development of all the cyber range training outcomes within. The aim of this Deliverable is to depict all relevant frameworks in order to assure that differing legal and regulatory constraints and internationally agreed standards for security, privacy and data protection are met. The deliverable will also include appropriate Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description		
EU	European Union	NIS	Networks and Information Systems
GA	Grant Agreement	HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
WP	Work Package	IT	Information Technology
IoT	The Internet of Things	OT	Operational Technology
DSA	Digital Security Authority	KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OUC	Open University of Cyprus	CIs	Critical Infrastructures
SPH	SPHYNX HELLAS	TNA	Training Needs Analysis
PPC	Public Power Corporation	WGs	Working Groups
OTE	Organismos Tilepikoinonion tis Ellados	ICT	Information and Communication Technology
MDG	Ministry Of Digital Governance	SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
PAGNI	Panepistimiako Geniko Nosokomeio Irakleiou	PII	Personally Identifiable Information
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation		

1. Introduction

1.1. Deliverable Objectives

The purpose of this deliverable is to gather key input from the critical domain stakeholders to assess their needs and expectations for the design of the SecAwarenessTruss cyber range training platform. Both quantitative (questionnaires) and qualitative (interviews) methods aim to further evaluate the current state of cybersecurity. Furthermore, it will involve a preliminary analysis of Cyber-range training requirements imposed by the existing national and European legal and regulatory framework and regime (NIS Directive and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and will also develop appropriate Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

1.2. Structure of This Document

Section 2 of this document first presents a general Cyber Security Training Requirements and Training Needs Analysis for the critical sectors related to the project. Secondly, it presents the Cyber Range Platform requirements survey through questionnaires and external stakeholder interviews. Section 3 provides the frame of Cyber Security and Privacy Regulations. In Section 4 appropriate Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are developed and finally, Section 5 provides the concluding remarks.

2. Cyber Security Training Requirements and Training Needs Analysis

Cybersecurity training is crucial for protecting critical sectors like telecommunication, energy, healthcare, and transportation from constantly evolving cyber threats. As these industries rely more on digital technologies and interconnected systems, the potential impact of cyberattacks increases significantly. Effective cybersecurity training programs are essential to equip employees with the skills and knowledge to identify, prevent, and respond to cyber threats. These programs should address specific vulnerabilities within each sector, adhere to regulatory requirements, and follow best practices to ensure a comprehensive approach to securing critical infrastructure. By investing in robust cybersecurity training, organizations can improve their resilience, safeguard sensitive data, and maintain the continuity and reliability of essential services.

Conducting a Training Needs Analysis (TNA) in any sector involves systematically assessing the knowledge, skills, and training requirements of its workforce to identify gaps and areas for improvement in cybersecurity readiness. Following is a possible approach to conducting a TNA across SecAwarenessTruss sectors^{1 2 3 4 5}:

- **Survey and Interviews:** Distribute surveys or conduct interviews with employees across different departments to gather feedback on their cybersecurity knowledge, skills, and training needs. Ask about their familiarity with security policies, procedures, and best practices, as well as areas where they feel they need additional training or support.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Key stakeholders should be engaged, including senior management, IT personnel, healthcare professionals, administrative staff, and compliance officers, to gain insight into their perspectives on cybersecurity training needs and priorities.
- **Review Regulatory Requirements:** It is essential to review applicable regulatory requirements and industry standards relevant to healthcare cybersecurity, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and cybersecurity frameworks like NIST Cybersecurity Framework. Identify specific training areas mandated by these regulations and standards.
- **Skills Assessment:** Assessing an employee's skills in critical cybersecurity areas, such as identifying phishing emails, securing patient data, using encryption tools, and responding to security incidents, is important. Analysing these results could help us to identify areas of strength and weakness across the workforce.
- **Role-Based Training Needs:** Recognize that different roles within the hospital may have varying training needs based on their responsibilities and level of interaction with patient data and healthcare systems. Tailor training programs to address specific job roles, such as clinicians, IT administrators, nurses, and administrative staff.
- **Gap Analysis:** Compare the desired level of cybersecurity knowledge and skills outlined in regulatory requirements, industry standards, and organisational objectives with employees'

1 https://www.internationaljournalofcaringsciences.org/docs/13_tsantili_original_14_1.pdf

2 <https://www.continu.com/blog/training-needs-analysis>

3 <https://1sthcc.com/10-best-practices-for-employee-training-in-healthcare/>

4 <https://405d.hhs.gov/Documents/405d-howto-cyberworkforcetraining-large.pdf>

5 <https://www.spamtitan.com/blog/effective-workforce-training-to-improve-cybersecurity-in-healthcare/>

current capabilities identified through the TNA. Identify gaps between the two to prioritise training areas and allocate resources effectively.

- **Emerging Threats and Technologies:** Each organisation should stay informed about emerging cybersecurity threats, trends, and technologies relevant to the healthcare sector. Consider how these developments may impact the hospital's training needs and adapt training programs accordingly to address new challenges and opportunities.

By conducting a comprehensive Training Needs Analysis, industries can gain valuable insights into their workforce's cybersecurity training requirements and develop targeted training programs to enhance cybersecurity awareness, readiness, and resilience across the organisation. Following next we present the training needs requirements and analysis for the four critical sectors of SecAwarenessTruss project.

2.1. Sector of Telecom

In today's dynamic digital landscape, telecommunications companies (telcos) are an integral part of digital frameworks by delivering connectivity not only for communication purposes but also for all sectors of the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) domain. Given the importance and the nature of the exchanged data, the telecom industry is a highly regulated sector and to this end, cyber security awareness and training of telecom staff is paramount to safeguarding networks, customer data, and critical infrastructure. The cyber security training requirements for the telecommunications industry involve addressing the increasing cyber threats faced by the sector⁶. The Cyber Threat landscape in the Telecom sector is presented in task D3.1, where an extensive analysis of all the relevant threats is provided.

Telecommunications companies need to implement robust breach detection and response mechanisms to mitigate the fallout of data breaches⁷. Although the deployment of highly scalable security mechanisms is the first part of protection, cyber security training is also another important factor in leveraging the security posture of a telco. As the telecom industry is a high-value target for cybercriminals, training should focus on understanding and responding to the evolving capabilities of cyber adversaries⁸. With the increasing deployment of IoT devices and the development of technologies like OpenRAN and 5G, the telecom sector faces new security risks and a wider attack surface for bad actors⁹. However, several common themes and guidelines emerge across the industry to create the following training needs:

Cybersecurity Awareness Training

Employees within the telecommunications sector should engage in routine training sessions to enhance their awareness of prevalent cyber threats, such as phishing attempts, malware, and social engineering tactics. This training should cover techniques for identifying potential threats and appropriate response procedures.

6 <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/commentary/article/improving-cybersecurity-outcomes-in-the-telecommunications-sector/>

7 <https://www.securitymagazine.com/articles/100586-navigating-cybersecurity-in-telecommunications-the-fccs-7-day-rule>

8 <https://www.ispartnersllc.com/blog/cybersecurity-telecommunications-sector/>

9 <https://techblog.comsoc.org/2022/12/31/cybersecurity-to-be-a-top-priority-for-telcos-in-2023/>

Regulatory Compliance Training

Telecommunications firms are frequently subject to various regulations regarding data security and privacy, including GDPR, HIPAA, or industry-specific standards like PCI-DSS (Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard). Employees need to understand their obligations regarding compliance with these regulations.

Technical Cybersecurity Training

Considering the critical nature of telecommunications networks, technical staff should participate in specialized training sessions addressing network security, secure coding practices, incident management, and penetration testing.

Risk Management Training

Employees in decision-making roles should undergo training on risk management principles relevant to cybersecurity, encompassing methodologies for risk assessment, strategies for risk mitigation, and the necessity of integrating cybersecurity into business operations.

Continuous Education and Updates

Given the ever-evolving nature of cyber threats, employees require ongoing educational efforts to stay informed about the latest threats, vulnerabilities, and best practices in cybersecurity.

Vendor and Partner Training

Telecommunications organizations often collaborate with vendors and partners who may have access to their systems or data. Training efforts should extend to these external entities to ensure a consistent approach to cybersecurity across the supply chain.

Network Security Fundamentals

Staff members should possess a solid understanding of essential network security principles, including encryption, authentication methods, access control mechanisms, and secure communication protocols.

Incident Response

Employees should be well-acquainted with incident response protocols to effectively manage and address security incidents, thus minimizing disruptions to operations and customer satisfaction.

2.2. Sector of Energy

The energy sector, pivotal in sustaining modern society, increasingly integrates advanced digital technologies like IoT, AI, and smart grid systems, dramatically expanding the complexity and scope of potential cyber threats. One of the primary reasons why cybersecurity is crucial in the energy sector is the critical nature of the infrastructure it supports. Any disruption to energy generation, transmission, or distribution can have profound consequences, ranging from localised power outages to widespread blackouts with significant economic and societal impacts. Cyber attacks targeting electrical energy systems can disrupt essential services, jeopardise public safety, and undermine national security, making robust cybersecurity measures imperative.

Moreover, the widespread integration of digital technologies and the implementation of smart grid systems have introduced novel vulnerabilities and avenues for attack within the electrical energy infrastructure. Devices connected to the internet, along with sensors and control systems, facilitate enhanced efficiency, real-time monitoring, and remote management of energy assets. Nevertheless, they also serve as potential entry points for cyber adversaries looking to exploit weaknesses and compromise critical systems. In the absence of robust cybersecurity defences, these interlinked systems are exposed to a range of cyber threats, including ransomware attacks, malware infections, and sophisticated cyber espionage campaigns.

Another crucial factor to consider is the interconnected nature of electrical energy systems with other essential infrastructure sectors, such as transportation, telecommunications, and water supply. Cyber attacks directed at any one sector can trigger cascading repercussions across interconnected systems, intensifying the impact and exacerbating disruptions. Therefore, securing electrical energy infrastructure is not only imperative for guaranteeing a dependable power supply but also for upholding the resilience and stability of the entire critical infrastructure ecosystem. This comprehensive overview explores specific training requirements and conducts a thorough Training Needs Analysis (TNA) to ensure preparedness.

Training needs for the energy sector can differ based on factors like the organization's size, industry segment, regulatory framework, and unique cybersecurity threats. Regular awareness campaigns are essential to keep personnel updated to the latest threats. Training material and sessions should be tailored to the different roles in the energy sector, from field technicians to senior management. Nonetheless, several typical training requirements are frequently applicable in the energy sector.

Regulatory Compliance Training

Employees should begin with an understanding of regulatory requirements pertinent to the energy sector, including the NERC CIP standards¹⁰ in the U.S., the EU's NIS2 Directive¹¹, the EU Network Code on Cybersecurity¹², GDPR¹³ and ISO 27001¹⁴. These requirements mandate robust cybersecurity measures to enhance the security and resilience of network and information systems across the energy sector.

Critical Infrastructure Protection Training

Personnel responsible for operating, maintaining, and overseeing crucial infrastructure elements like power plants, substations, and transmission lines, should undergo specialised training in critical infrastructure safeguarding. This training might encompass comprehension of the distinct cybersecurity challenges confronting critical infrastructure, deployment of security measures, and response strategies for cyber incidents.

Operational Technology (OT) Security Training

Cover the specific security considerations for industrial control systems and smart infrastructure, including regular updates on the latest threats specific to OT and best practices for securing these

10 <https://www.nerc.com/pa/Stand/Pages/ReliabilityStandards.aspx>

11 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2555>

12 <https://www.entsoe.eu/news/2024/05/24/first-network-code-on-cybersecurity-for-the-electricity-sector-published-today/>

13 <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/>

14 <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso-iec:27001:ed-2:v1:en>

environments. The training should address the vulnerabilities specific to ageing technology and the unique threats posed by interconnected systems and control systems security, such as ransomware attacks.

Incident Response Training

Personnel engaged in incident response duties, like cybersecurity analysts, incident responders, and IT personnel, ought to undergo targeted training in incident response protocols. This training might entail simulated scenarios, tabletop exercises, and practical sessions to equip them with the skills to detect, manage, and mitigate cybersecurity incidents proficiently by minimising potential damage and restoring systems promptly.

Data Security and Privacy Training

Employees responsible for handling sensitive data, such as customer information, employee records, and intellectual property should receive training emphasising secure management of smart grid data, encryption practices, and comprehensive risk management strategies to protect against data breaches and insider threats. The integration of IT and OT systems expands the attack surface, making this training essential.

Business Continuity Processes Training

Training staff to develop and implement effective recovery plans that address both cyber and physical disruptions. These plans should outline clear steps to restore critical operations swiftly to minimise downtime. Conducting regular simulation exercises that mimic potential disruption scenarios based on cyberattacks. Finally employ regular updates to the business continuity plans to reflect the changing threat landscape and new technological integrations.

Third-Party Risk Management Training

Personnel engaged in vendor management, procurement, and supply chain oversight should undergo training in third-party risk management protocols. This training might involve evaluating the cybersecurity stance of vendors and suppliers, setting contractual cybersecurity standards, and overseeing the security performance of third parties.

Executive Cybersecurity Awareness Training

Executives and senior leaders should undergo tailored training in cybersecurity governance, risk management, and compliance. This training might involve comprehending the business implications of cybersecurity risks, aligning cybersecurity endeavours with business goals, and cultivating a security-centric culture across the organisation.

By implementing targeted training initiatives, organizations in the energy sector can bolster their cybersecurity readiness, thus diminishing the likelihood of security breaches and incidents. Moreover, the enhancement of technical competencies among employees facilitates heightened operational efficiency and optimized performance of energy infrastructure. Adherence to regulatory mandates like NERC CIP, GDPR, and ISO 27001 not only ensures compliance with legal and industry standards but also reinforces overall security posture.

Furthermore, effective training aimed at addressing human errors serves as a crucial measure in mitigating cybersecurity incidents, thereby reducing overall risk. Additionally, investments in employee development not only cultivate higher levels of engagement and job satisfaction within the organization but also contribute to a more resilient and secure energy sector. Together, these

efforts culminate in a fortified and secure energy sector, better equipped to confront the evolving challenges posed by cybersecurity threats and regulatory compliance requirements.

2.3. Sector of Healthcare

The healthcare sector, like all other critical sectors, is heavily dependent on new technologies (e.g., e-Services, Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), etc.) by adopting the latest digital methods to operate in all the facilities of the health organizations. In addition, the typical business operations of healthcare organizations (administration, finance, communication, filing, etc.) also manage interconnected medical e-systems and smart devices.

Multiple stakeholders must have access to the healthcare systems, either from inside or outside (remote access) of the organization's infrastructure. E-hospitals, or "smart hospitals"¹⁵, have been established as a result of the advancement of digitization. These facilities provide patients with improved health services, including quicker and more accurate diagnosis, treatment, and health monitoring. The potential targets of cyberattacks have grown concurrently with the proliferation of e-medical devices and services. Health organizations are easy targets for cyberattacks because they handle sensitive patient data, or personally identifiable information (PII), and the urge to have non-interrupted availability of healthcare services.

Unfortunately, for healthcare organizations, cybersecurity is not a priority for their investment – a common issue in many other domains (e.g., education, tourism, and agriculture). Low budget for cybersecurity materials and training, often results in using legacy medical systems in health organizations as well as software incompatible with the latest security properties. An IT expert team in a health organization does not necessarily include personnel with advanced cybersecurity skills.

Furthermore, healthcare stakeholders, especially doctors, nurses, and other health professionals work under pressure in emergencies and very stressful environments, with strict working schedules (night shifts, on-call shifts). Time availability is an obstacle for both IT and non-IT experts and healthcare personnel to attend cybersecurity awareness training that could aid in strengthening the cybersecurity status of the organization.

There are recent reports that pointed out the aforementioned cybersecurity gap in infrastructure, training, and also investments in cybersecurity, in general^{16 17}.

Identifying specific training requirements for the healthcare sector involves understanding the unique cybersecurity challenges and compliance obligations faced by healthcare organizations. Below you can find an analysis of possible training requirements^{18 19 20 21}:

15 <https://ictandhealth.com/news/saudi-arabia-brings-worlds-first-virtual-hospital-to-life>

16 <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/training-and-exercises/cyber-exercises/cyber-europe-programme/cyber-europe-2022>

17 <https://csirtsnetwork.eu/>

18 <https://elearningindustry.com/elearning-for-the-healthcare-industry-addressing-critical-training-needs>

19 <https://1sthcc.com/10-best-practices-for-employee-training-in-healthcare/>

20 <https://meriplex.com/cybersecurity-awareness-training-healthcare/>

21 <https://expertinsights.com/insights/security-awareness-training-for-healthcare-organizations-a-comprehensive-guide/>

Regulatory Requirements training:

Begin by identifying regulatory requirements and industry standards relevant to cybersecurity in the healthcare sector. This may include regulations such as the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and industry standards such as the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Cybersecurity Framework.

Data Security and Privacy Training

Hospital employees should receive training on best practices for safeguarding patient data and maintaining data privacy. This may include training on encryption techniques, secure handling of electronic health records (EHRs), password management, and protection against insider threats.

Phishing Awareness Training

Given the prevalence of phishing attacks in the healthcare sector, employees should be trained to recognize and respond to phishing emails. Training should cover common phishing techniques, red flags to watch for, and procedures for reporting suspicious emails or phishing attempts.

Secure Remote Access Training

With the increasing use of telemedicine and remote work in healthcare, employees should receive training on secure remote access practices. This includes guidance on using virtual private networks (VPNs), multi-factor authentication (MFA), and secure communication tools to protect patient data when working remotely.

Incident Response Training

Hospital staff should be trained on how to respond effectively to cybersecurity incidents and data breaches. This training should include procedures for identifying and reporting security incidents, mitigating the impact of breaches, and collaborating with IT security teams and regulatory authorities during incident response efforts.

Medical Device Security Training

Healthcare professionals and IT personnel responsible for managing medical devices should receive training on medical device security best practices. This includes understanding the security risks associated with network-connected medical devices, implementing appropriate security controls, and conducting regular vulnerability assessments and patch management.

Cybersecurity training should be an ongoing process, with regular refresher courses and updates to keep employees informed about emerging threats, new security technologies, and changes to regulatory requirements. Training programs should be tailored to different roles and departments within the hospital to address specific training needs effectively.

2.4. Sector of Maritime

Cybersecurity threats are increasingly sophisticated and complex, posing significant challenges for defenders to detect and respond in a timely manner. National critical infrastructures, often targeted by these threats, play a crucial role in maintaining national security and ensuring the continuity of supply chains. A compromise in these infrastructures can lead to widespread societal disruptions. The maritime domain, integral to global trade and logistics, presents a high-value target for cyber adversaries. The impact of cyber-attacks in this sector can severely affect shipping industries, ports, and other critical maritime infrastructures. Recent studies have underscored various cybersecurity risks^{22 23 24} within the maritime sector, highlighting the need for comprehensive Maritime Cyber Situational Awareness (MCSA) to address these challenges effectively across strategic, operational, and technical levels.

Many standards and guidelines aim to bolster the security of information systems, with some tailored specifically for the maritime sector. Despite these resources, there exists a pressing need for enhanced cybersecurity awareness within the industry. This awareness is crucial for understanding cyber risks and implementing effective cyber risk management strategies. Empowering decision-makers to select and apply relevant cybersecurity regulations and frameworks is vital. Such frameworks should align with their organisation's needs, facilitating the development of robust cybersecurity strategies. Consequently, cybersecurity education and training programs must incorporate content that builds the necessary knowledge and skills to navigate these challenges. This section identifies relevant cybersecurity regulations and frameworks applicable in the maritime domain, aiding organisations in selecting the most appropriate ones based on their operational environment and specific needs.

A critical component in defining cybersecurity training requirements is the assessment of existing legislative and regulatory frameworks. To this end, key publications from organisations such as the International Maritime Organization (IMO), the Baltic and International Maritime Council (BIMCO), the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), and the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) have been identified:

- IMO: Resolution MSC.428(98), Maritime Cyber Risk Management in Safety Management Systems²⁵
- IMO: MSC-FAL.1/Circ.3, Guidelines on Maritime Cyber Risk Management²⁶

22 G. Potamos, S. Theodoulou, E. Stavrou, S. Stavrou, Building maritime cybersecurity capacity against ransomware attacks, Proceedings of the International Conference on Cybersecurity, Situational Awareness and Social Media: Cyber Science 2022, 20–21 June, Wales

23 G. Potamos, S. Theodoulou, E. Stavrou, S. Stavrou, Maritime cyber threats detection framework: Building capabilities, IFIP World Conference on Information Security Education (WISE), 2022

24 G. Potamos, E. Stavrou, S. Stavrou, JC Lopez, A. Eyzaguirre, C A. Runyan-Beebe, P. Macias, Increase maritime cyber situational awareness at a strategic level, 15th International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation (ICERI), 2022

25 IMO: Resolution MSC.428(98), Maritime Cyber Risk Management in Safety Management Systems, [https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/OurWork/Security/Documents/Resolution%20MSC.428\(98\).pdf](https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/OurWork/Security/Documents/Resolution%20MSC.428(98).pdf)

26 IMO: MSC-FAL.1/Circ.3, Guidelines on Maritime Cyber Risk Management, [https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/OurWork/Security/Documents/MS-C-FAL.1-Circ.3-Rev.2%20-%20Guidelines%20On%20Maritime%20Cyber%20Risk%20Management%20\(Secretariat\).pdf](https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/OurWork/Security/Documents/MS-C-FAL.1-Circ.3-Rev.2%20-%20Guidelines%20On%20Maritime%20Cyber%20Risk%20Management%20(Secretariat).pdf)

- BIMCO: The Guidelines on Cyber Security Onboard Ships²⁷
- ENISA: Guidelines - Cyber Risk Management for Ports²⁸
- NIST: Various frameworks and guides, including the Risk Management Framework (RMF)²⁹, the Cybersecurity Framework (CSF)³⁰, and guidelines for Operational Technology (OT) Security³¹

The specified security and safety requirements, guided by international regulations, provide a structured approach for implementing cybersecurity best practices and strategies and driving the design of training curricula that can enable the practical application of the frameworks' guidelines. Considering the available publications, the training curricula should span both horizontal and vertical knowledge areas, covering Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) systems relevant to different operational roles involved in maritime operations such as C-Level executives, captains, IT managers, operators, first engineers, etc. Overall, the training needs that are identified and which are essential to enhance maritime cybersecurity include:

Cybersecurity Awareness Training

Comprehensive programs to raise awareness about cyber threats and safe practices among all employees, not just those directly involved with IT or cybersecurity. This training is particularly essential for all non-IT personnel, focusing on the basics of cybersecurity, the importance of safeguarding systems, and recognizing common cyber threats such as phishing.

Technical Cybersecurity Training

Specialised training for IT and cybersecurity teams that covers the specific technologies and security measures used in port operations, including both Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) systems.

Incident Response Training

Personnel such as crew members, IT and cybersecurity teams need to be trained on procedures and actions to take in the event of a cybersecurity incident, focusing on how to effectively identify, respond, contain, and mitigate potential damages and recover from attacks.

Risk Assessment and Management Training

This involves training designated personnel on conducting and updating risk assessments, understanding the ship's vulnerabilities, and implementing effective mitigation strategies.

27 BIMCO: The Guidelines on Cyber Security Onboard Ships, <https://www.bimco.org/about-us-and-our-members/publications/the-guidelines-on-cyber-security-onboard-ships>

28 ENISA: Guidelines - Cyber Risk Management for Ports, <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/guidelines-cyber-risk-management-for-ports>

29 NIST SP 800-37 Rev. 2 - Risk Management Framework for Information Systems and Organizations: A System Life Cycle Approach for Security and Privacy, <https://csrc.nist.gov/pubs/sp/800/37/r2/final>

30 NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0, <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/CSWP/NIST.CSWP.29.pdf>

31 NIST SP 800-82 Rev. 3 - Guide to Operational Technology (OT) Security, <https://csrc.nist.gov/pubs/sp/800/82/r3/final>

Regulatory Compliance Training

Training on national and international cybersecurity regulations and standards that affect maritime operations, ensuring compliance and understanding of legal responsibilities.

Interdepartmental Training

Encouraging collaboration across different departments (e.g., IT, operations, security) to ensure a unified approach to cybersecurity, recognizing the interconnected nature of modern port operations.

Addressing the above training needs can contribute to building a robust cybersecurity culture across the maritime ecosystem, ensuring that all personnel understand their roles and responsibilities in safeguarding the relevant digital and physical infrastructures of the ecosystem.

Utilising a maritime Cyber Range as a dedicated training infrastructure will be beneficial to support comprehensive cybersecurity exercises specified in the context of offensive and defensive training scenarios. Such a training infrastructure can support a range of learning objectives to enhance the capabilities of IT and non-IT personnel. Training scenarios should take into consideration typical systems and networks found in a maritime environment such as administrative IT networks (onboard and ashore), entertainment networks, and navigation/surveillance systems. Focus should be given to cybersecurity aspects related to critical systems such as GNSS, Radars, AIS, and ECDIS for scenario development. The overall training objective should be to improve personnel's competencies through authentic training scenarios that spotlight vulnerabilities in maritime IT and OT systems. A diverse type of training material, e.g. walkthroughs, demonstrations, hands-on exercises, etc., should also be developed to support the trainees' learning styles and meet their expertise.

2.5. Cyber Range Platform Requirements survey

2.5.1. Questionnaires

The following section provides an overview of the online survey. In particular, conducting an online cybersecurity survey via questionnaires is crucial for gathering comprehensive data on an organization's current cybersecurity practices, awareness levels, and specific training needs. It enables the identification of vulnerabilities and gaps in existing security measures, providing insights into areas requiring improvement. Such surveys facilitate benchmarking against industry standards and peers, ensuring that organizations stay updated with best practices. Additionally, by engaging diverse stakeholders, these surveys inform targeted and effective cybersecurity strategies, enhancing the overall readiness and resilience of the organization against cyber threats.

SecAwarenessTruss Consortium, to further explore the cybersecurity training needs of the critical sectors stakeholders, designed and implemented online questionnaires³² addressed to different types of personnel: IT and Non-IT^{33 34}. These questionnaires are presented in the Annex I.

2.5.1.1. Preliminary Analysis - Non-IT Questionnaire

The questionnaire results reveal a varied range of roles within participating organizations, prominently featuring IT related staff, healthcare professionals, and security personnel, illustrating the multidisciplinary nature of cybersecurity efforts in critical sectors. Most respondents have more than 10 years of experience in their current roles, indicating a relatively stable and experienced workforce. The majority of respondents come from Enterprise organizations, especially within the Telecoms, Energy and Healthcare sector, which underscores the critical need for robust cybersecurity measures to protect sensitive patient information and comply with regulatory requirements.

When it comes to cybersecurity awareness and training, the frequency of updates on new threats and safety practices is quite diverse. The majority of organizations provide updates every one month to one year, ensuring that employees are periodically informed about emerging cybersecurity challenges and best practices. Monthly updates are also present, reflecting a proactive stance towards cybersecurity education. One valuable observation is that approximately 50% of employees are not informed or they are not getting at all cybersecurity threats and safety practices updates within their organization.

Most of the respondents are aware that their organization has a strong cybersecurity framework in place, with dedicated personnel. They must regularly change their password for work-related accounts, they use specific antivirus software at work, are aware of the risks associated with public Wi-Fi, and know what to do in the event that they lose a work device.

The reality shows also that more than 50% of respondents have never participated in a simulated phishing exercise, they don't know their organization's constraints, they don't know how often critical data is backed up and have either witnessed or experienced a cybersecurity incident.

This disparity points to the need for a more standardized approach to cybersecurity training and awareness across the sectors. These insights suggest that while many organizations are making significant efforts to keep their workforce informed and prepared, there is still room for improvement to ensure comprehensive coverage and consistent training.

Overall, these findings emphasize the importance of developing and implementing tailored cybersecurity training programs that address the specific needs of various roles and sectors. Such programs should aim to provide regular, up-to-date information on cybersecurity threats and safety

32 <https://secawarenesstruss.eu/news/secawarenesstruss-cyber-range-questionnaires/>

33 <https://www.jotform.com/blog/cybersecurity-questionnaires/>

34 <https://www.startquestion.com/survey-ideas/sample-survey-cybersecurity-questionnaire/>

practices to enhance the overall security posture of organizations. Ensuring that all employees, regardless of their role or tenure, are equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills to protect sensitive data and respond effectively to cyber incidents is crucial for maintaining robust cybersecurity defenses.

2.5.1.2. Preliminary Analysis - IT Questionnaire

The questionnaire gathers comprehensive data on the cybersecurity training needs and practices of IT professionals. It covers various aspects including the respondents' roles, years of experience, organization size, and sector. Key areas of focus include regulations and standards, cyber range platform features, perceived training effectiveness, and specific areas where further training is required. The insights aim to inform the development of targeted and effective cybersecurity training programs to enhance the overall security posture of organizations. The structure of the analysis is based on the relevant sections of the questionnaire:

- **General Information**

Although respondents hold a variety of positions, the majority are in Research and Development and as IT/Cybersecurity professionals. They mostly represent Enterprise organizations, most of which have a strong cybersecurity framework in place, and their main cybersecurity concern is distributed among all answers provided. It's also important to note that the majority of them do not follow any standards, regulations, or guidelines in their cybersecurity practices.

- **Cyber Range Understanding and Expectations**

Over 50% of the participants are somewhat familiar with the concept of Cyber Ranges and believe that these platforms will offer realistic simulation environments for training, R&D, improving incident response and cybersecurity skills.

- **Specific Needs and Characteristics**

The survey highlights the need for training tailored to specific roles and industry requirements. According to some common responses, it's necessary to simulate certain cyberthreats, such as ransomware (75,61%), install Cyber Range platform primarily On premise or Hybrid, with an infinite number of users for an infinite amount of time, and have the ability to save and resume a scenario's virtual machines. Furthermore, almost all of the potential responses to our questions concerning the capabilities of the Cyber Range platform were provided, which indicates that we should incorporate as many features as we can to improve the training. It is worth mentioning here that the most significant obstacles to implementing or participating in a Cyber Range are organizational difficulties, lack of personnel and lack of funding across all the sectors of interest.

- **Training and Development**

Everyone agrees that using a training platform to increase a trainee's skills or competencies is essential. The majority of answers recommend abilities like management, security awareness, network and system administration, and policy and procedure establishment. Almost all of the first four answers were provided in the same percentage when it came to assessing the success of a Cyber Range training exercise.

- **Collaboration and Information Sharing**

Respondents acknowledge the importance of collaboration and information sharing among different sectors and organizations. They support initiatives that facilitate knowledge exchange and joint cybersecurity exercises to improve collective defense mechanisms when non sensitive data are exchanged.

- **Feedback and Additional Comments**

Feedback suggests a demand for more interactive and engaging training methods, including gamified learning, phishing campaigns and real-time threat simulations and analytics. There is also a call for an improved response scenario in case of a crisis and a disaster recovery plan exercise including natural disasters, and system failures.

In Annex II we present the current statics analysis of the questionnaires as extracted from EU Survey platform³⁵.

2.5.2. External stakeholders interview

Conducting interviews with external stakeholders as part of a Training Needs Analysis (TNA) for an organization's cybersecurity training program can be highly beneficial for several reasons like Industry Insights, Benchmarking, Regulatory Guidance, Vendor Perspective, and Collaboration Opportunities. A presentation outlining the project will be shown during these interviews. The external stakeholders will then complete the IT experts' questionnaire at the conclusion of the interview.

For the healthcare sector, these interviews will take place during Working Groups (WGs) with other hospitals in the Region of Crete that will be formed specifically for this purpose.

Interviews for the maritime sector may be held separately for maritime stakeholders. Interviews may also be held during WGs with other maritime stakeholders which will be arranged for this purpose.

For the energy sector, these interviews may be conducted during Working Groups (WGs) with other energy providers and infrastructure operators in the region. Separate interviews may also be held with key energy facilities. Additionally, interviews can be organized during WGs with other energy sector stakeholders, specifically arranged for this purpose.

For the Telecom sector, interviews will be conducted with companies extracted from a list of B2B marketplace of OTE. This list contains companies receiving ICT cyber security services.

A substantial number of interviews have been conducted up until the date of the deliverable submission, however, these will continue, and the deliverable D3.3 will contain a more detailed presentation of the findings.

³⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome>

3. Cyber Security and Privacy Regulations

3.1. General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR

The European Union is one of the most influential international organizations which operates under a system of Conventions and Treaties that are compulsory for its member states in specific fields. In general, this system overrules national legislative frameworks in cases of conflict. For this reason, national legislative systems have been harmonized and in certain matters unified. As a response to the rapid development of emerging technologies, in recent years EU legislators have reformed EU data protection regulations to empower European citizens to exercise their rights regarding the processing of their personal data. The highlight of these reforms was the adoption of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁴. Its text was finalized on 8 April 2016 and approved by the European Parliament on 14 April 2016. Subsequently, it was adopted on 27 April 2016, and entered into force on 24 May 2016, applying from 25 May 2018. Apart from empowering European citizens concerning their data protection rights, the GDPR provides a singular system of personal data protection for all 28 Member States.

Consequently, regulating new technologies, systems, and frameworks, is more relevant now than ever before. Regulators must confront the challenge of balancing between responsible innovation and the use of technologies for the public interest. In many respects, the cross-border movement of services and goods produces a need for the harmonization of national legislative frameworks and the coordination of self-restraint mechanisms by the Member States.

Although this regulation is not designed for cyber security purposes, the GDPR is a good guide to properly address security (and data protection) at an earlier stage. It establishes the principle of accountability, where each company is responsible for its implementation and legal responsibility. Considering the relevant legislation in Greece, we propose that, within the process of this project, GDPR guidelines be addressed as part of improvements in the cyber security baseline³⁶.

Within the design of the SecAwarenessTruss Cyber Range Platform, special consideration should be given to the fact that the interaction with personal data requires a legal basis. The considerations should be addressed and also should be taken into account during the development process. If possible, security by design should prevent the interaction with personal data.

3.2. Networks and Information Systems Directives – NIS & NIS2

The European Union has developed a framework of regulations to govern cybersecurity matters, guiding authorities, operators, incident response teams, and other relevant stakeholders in assessing cyber risks and handling cyber incidents. The cornerstone of this framework was the EU Directive 2016/1148 (NIS Directive), which mandates certain cybersecurity measures for entities of essential services, aiming to elevate the level of preparedness of all Member States. Lately, the NIS

³⁶https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5f294433d3bf7f1b18aaad27/Impact_of_GDPR_on_cyber_security_outcomes.pdf

Directive was replaced by the EU Directive 2022/2555 (NIS2 Directive), published in the Official Journal of the EU in January 2023^{37 38 39}.

The NIS Directive imposed a minimum baseline set of cybersecurity capabilities for Member States and their Operators of Essential Services while providing cross-border coordination and cooperation. To incorporate and implement the NIS Directive, Member States have defined reporting and information-sharing procedures between National Competent Authorities and the Operators of Essential Services.

The NIS2 Directive, waiting to be transposed by Member States no later than October 2024, aims to enhance cybersecurity resilience by introducing greater capabilities, cooperation, and strengthened security requirements, while expanding its scope to include more sectors and services. Entities falling within the scope of the Directive are classified into two categories, essential entities and important entities, reflecting the extent to which they are critical as regards their sector or the type of service they provide, as well as their size. The Directive sets out the baseline for cybersecurity risk management with a list of focused measures including incident response and crisis management, vulnerability handling and disclosure, cybersecurity testing, and the effective use of encryption.

For the first time, cybersecurity rules in the ICT supply chain are defined by the NIS2 Directive. Furthermore, inconsistencies in the internal market are reduced by further aligning the scope, the security and incident reporting requirements, the provisions governing national supervision and enforcement, and the capabilities of the competent authorities of the Member States. The NIS2 Directive improves the level of shared situational awareness through measures to increase the level of trust and the sharing of information between competent authorities, and sets out rules and procedures in the event of a large-scale incident or crisis, introducing clear responsibilities, proper planning, and closer cooperation at the EU level.

The NIS Directive provided the Member States with wide discretion as regards the implementation of the security and incident reporting obligations laid down therein. The NIS2 Directive streamlines incident reporting obligations with more precise reporting process, content, and timeline provisions.

More specifically, The NIS2 is bringing the following new requirements for organizations falling under its scope:

- It stipulates that all medium and large entities operating in the sectors covered by the Directive's framework must comply with the safety rules. It removes the possibility for Member States to adapt the requirements according to their views.

37 Directive 2022/2555, Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive), <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2555/oj>

38 Directive 2016/1148, Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union, <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/1148/oj>

39 European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Hitting the refresh button on cybersecurity rules – NIS2 – Proposal for a directive on measures for high common level of cybersecurity across the union, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/0630>

- Entities will need to report to their CSIRT or competent authority in a multi-stage manner, to strike the right balance between swift reporting, to mitigate the spreading of significant incidents, and in-depth reporting, that will help derive valuable lessons and improve cyber resilience.
- Entities must notify their users about identified cyber threats and associated measures to be taken in response.
- Entities must maintain constant vigilance for threats and vulnerabilities that could affect their services.
- Entities need to develop, test, and establish business continuity plans.
- Entities must provide advanced cybersecurity training methodologies to their employees, to improve the overall security posture of the organisation.
- Entities should be capable of sharing and exchanging information for coordinated threat handling and incident response, efficiently.
- Management bodies of essential and important entities should approve the cybersecurity risk-management measures taken by those entities and oversee its implementation. Management bodies can be held liable for infringements of the Directive.

4. Key Performance Indicators

In today's dynamic business environment, the ability to measure and track performance is crucial for organizations striving to achieve their strategic objectives. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) serve as powerful tools in this endeavor, providing clear and quantifiable metrics to gauge progress and success. Setting KPIs in this deliverable is essential for ensuring accountability, driving performance improvement, and ultimately achieving project success. By defining clear and measurable metrics that align with project goals and objectives, organizations can effectively track progress, monitor performance, and make informed decisions to optimize outcomes.

No.	Project Obj. Description	Relevant WP	KPI Description	To be verified
KPI#01	<p>Objective:1</p> <p>To deliver a state-of-the-art platform that considerably extends the capabilities of existing cybersecurity ranges and structure training framework for effective cyber defence.</p>	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5	Customization of federate cybersecurity ranges in the targeted critical infrastructure organization	D2.3, D3.3, D4.2, D5.2
KPI#02	<p>Objective:1</p> <p>To deliver a state-of-the-art platform that considerably extends the capabilities of existing cybersecurity ranges and structure training framework for effective cyber defence..</p>	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5	Interconnection among cybersecurity ranges from targeted critical infrastructure organizations	D2.2, D2.3, D5.1
KPI#03	<p>Objective:1</p> <p>To deliver a state-of-the-art platform that considerably extends the capabilities of existing cybersecurity ranges and structure training framework for effective cyber defence.</p>	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5	Training needs assessment based on at least four targeted trainee groups	D2.2, D2.3, D4.2, D5.2
KPI#04	<p>Objective 2:</p> <p>Develop and deliver innovative and hands-on training curricula for a sustainable training program to support the critical infrastructure sector.</p>	WP2 WP3	Creating at least 10 different training modules and related curricula	D3.3, D4.2

KPI#05	Objective 2: Develop and deliver innovative and hands-on training curricula for a sustainable training program to support the critical infrastructure sector.	WP2 WP3	Coverage of at least 4 critical infrastructure sectors	D3.3, D4.1, D4.2
KPI#06	Objective 2: Develop and deliver innovative and hands-on training curricula for a sustainable training program to support the critical infrastructure sector.	WP2 WP3	Engagement a total of at least 225 trainees for the training activities	D5.1, D5.2
KPI#07	Develop realistic large scale and cross sector scenarios with gaming exercise	WP3	Creating at least 3 cross-sector scenarios based on 4 critical infrastructure organisation	D2.2, D3.3, D5.2
KPI#08	Objective 3: Develop realistic large scale and cross sector scenarios with gaming exercise	WP3	Integration of at least 4 gaming cybersecurity exercises per scenario	D2.2, D3.3, D5.2
KPI#09	Objective 4: Share threat intelligence knowledge for a coordinated cyber-incident response and create common data repository among the CI organisations	WP4 WP5	Improve the capabilities of the critical infrastructure organisation operators to exchange information	D4.1, D4.2
KPI#10	Objective 4: Share threat intelligence knowledge for a coordinated cyber-incident response and create common data repository among the CI organisations	WP4 WP5	Successful exchange of information among the connected ranges	D5.2
KPI#11	Objective 4: Share threat intelligence knowledge for a coordinated cyber-incident response and create a common data repository among the CI organisations	WP4 WP5	At least 2 common security-related data repository	D4.1, D4.2
KPI#12	Objective 5: Evaluate and strengthen Cybersecurity ranges and	WP4 WP5	measure in % the change in the	D5.2

	develop best practices and Guidelines for wider range adaptation across Europe		capacity of the cybersecurity ranges after pilot operation	
KPI#13	Objective 5: Evaluate and strengthen Cybersecurity ranges and develop best practices and Guidelines for wider range adaptation across Europe	WP4 WP5	Successful completion of at least 4 pilot operations	D5.2
KPI#14	Objective 6: Improve the security awareness level of employees	WP5	Measuring in % the Effectiveness of Security Awareness Training	D5.2
KPI#15	Objective 7: Share current information status from the different sectors of the project.	WP2 WP4	To provide a unified dashboard	D2.3, D4.1, D4.2

Table 1 SecAwarenessTruss KPIs

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, the comprehensive analysis of training and cyber range capabilities and requirements in the critical sectors of telecommunications, energy, healthcare, and maritime underscores the imperative for robust cybersecurity preparedness. As these sectors continue to evolve in an increasingly digital landscape, the need for effective training programs and cyber range platforms becomes paramount to safeguarding critical infrastructure and sensitive data from emerging threats. By identifying and addressing the specific requirements of each sector, organizations can enhance their resilience to cyber attacks, mitigate potential risks, and ensure uninterrupted operations. Moreover, investing in advanced training methodologies and state-of-the-art cyber range facilities not only strengthens the cybersecurity posture of individual sectors but also contributes to the overall resilience and security of the national infrastructure. Moving forward, ongoing collaboration, innovation, and adaptation will be essential to staying ahead of evolving cyber threats and safeguarding the vital services upon which society relies.

SecAwarenessTruss Questionnaire For Non-IT Professionals

SecAwarenessTruss Cyber Security Training Requirements For Non-IT Professionals

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

* 1 Your Role in the Organization (Please specify):

* 2 How many years do you have in your current role?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Less than a year
- 1-3 years
- 4-6 years
- 7-10 years
- More than 10 years

* 3 What is the size of your organization?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Small (1-50 employees)
- Medium (51-200 employees)
- Large (201-500 employees)
- Enterprise (501+ employees)

* 4 Which sector does your organization operate in? (Please select the most relevant)

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Energy
- Finance

- Government
- Healthcare
- Maritime
- Telecoms

5 Other (please specify)

* 6 How often does your organization update you on new cybersecurity threats and safety practices?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Every month
- Every six months
- Every year
- Every two years
- More than two years
- Unsure/Don't know

* 7 How would you rate your organization's current cybersecurity posture?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Very advanced - we are at the cutting edge of cybersecurity practices
- Advanced - we have a strong cybersecurity framework in place
- Moderate - we are doing okay but could improve
- Basic - we are somewhat vulnerable and need to do more
- Unsure/Don't know

* 8 Does your organisation have a dedicated team or individual responsible for cybersecurity?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No
- Unsure/Don't know

* 9 Have you ever experienced or witnessed a cybersecurity incident (e.g., data breach, malware attack) in your organisation?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No
- Unsure/Don't know

* 10 Does your organization require regular password changes for work-related accounts and systems?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No
- Unsure/Don't know

* 11 Does your organisation restrict the use of external devices (e.g., USB drives, personal smartphones) on work devices?

2

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No
- Unsure/Don't know

- * 12 Does your organisation use anti-virus or anti-malware software on work devices?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No
- Unsure/Don't know

- * 13 Are you aware of what to do if you lose a work device (e.g., laptop, smartphone)?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No
- Unsure/Don't know

- * 14 Are you aware of the risks associated with using public Wi-Fi networks for work-related activities?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No
- Unsure/Don't know

- * 15 Has your organisation ever conducted a simulated phishing exercise to test employee awareness?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No
- Unsure/Don't know

- * 16 Do you know how frequently does your organisation back up critical data?

- Every day
- Every week
- Every month
- Every six months
- Unsure/Don't know

SecAwarenessTruss Questionnaire For IT Professionals

SecAwarenessTruss Cyber Security Training Requirements For IT Professionals

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

General Information

* 1 Your Role in the Organization:

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Executive Management
- IT/Cybersecurity Professional
- Operational Technology (OT) Professional
- Research and Development
- Other

2 Other (Please specify):

* 3 How many years have you been working in your current role?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Less than a year
- 1-3 years
- 4-6 years
- 7-10 years
- More than 10 years

* 4 What is the size of your organization?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

1

- Small (1-50 employees)
- Medium (51-200 employees)
- Large (201-500 employees)
- Enterprise (501+ employees)

* 5 Which sector does your organization operate in? (Please select the most relevant)

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Energy
- Telecommunications
- Healthcare
- Maritime
- Government
- Finance
- Other

6 Other (please specify):

* 7 What is your primary cybersecurity concern? (Select all that apply)

- Protecting customer data
- Ensuring system availability
- Compliance with regulatory requirements
- Preventing ransomware attacks
- Safeguarding intellectual property
- Employee training and awareness
- Other

8 Other (Please specify):

* 9 How would you rate your organization's current cybersecurity posture?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Very advanced - we are at the cutting edge of cybersecurity practices
- Advanced - we have a strong cybersecurity framework in place
- Moderate - we are doing okay but could improve
- Basic - we are somewhat vulnerable and need to do more
- Unsure/Don't know

* 10 Which of the below standards, regulations, and/or guidelines are you utilizing as part of your cybersecurity practices:

- ISO/IEC 27001
- ISO/IEC 27002
- ISO/IEC 27005
- ISO/IEC 27017

- ISO/IEC 27018
- ISO/IEC 27701
- NIST SP 800-30
- NIST SP 800-53
- NIST's Cybersecurity Framework
- IMO: Resolution MSC.428(98)
- IMO: MSC-FAL.1/Circ.3
- BIMCO
- None
- Don't know
- Other

Cyber Range Understanding and Expectations

* 11 How familiar are you with the concept and functionalities of Cyber Ranges?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Very Familiar
- Somewhat Familiar
- Not Familiar

* 12 What are your primary objectives for utilizing a Cyber Range? (Select all that apply)

- Training and enhancing cybersecurity skills
- Testing system resilience to cyber-attacks
- Conducting cybersecurity research and development
- Simulating cyber incident response
- Other

13 Other (Please specify):

Specific Needs and Characteristics

* 14 Which features do you consider crucial for a Cyber Range? (Select all that apply)

- Simulation of specialised/OT systems (e.g., SCADA)
- Capability to simulate specific types of cyber threats (e.g., ransomware, APTs)
- Integration with existing IT/OT infrastructure for realistic testing
- Support for collaborative exercises with other organizations
- Automated feedback and performance evaluation tools
- Compliance testing with regulatory standards (e.g., NIS2, NIST SP800-82, ISA/IEC 62443, GDPR)
- Other

15 Other (Please specify):

* 16 What would be the ideal location of a Cyber Range for you:

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- On premise
- Cloud- based (remote)
- Hybrid (blend of on premise and cloud- based)
- Mobile and portable solution

* 17 The Cyber Range should support:

- Limited number of users for a limited time period
- Limited number of users for an unlimited time period
- Unlimited number of users for a limited time period
- Unlimited number of users for an unlimited time period
- Interoperability with remote orchestrators, scenarios
- Possibility to federate with other scenarios

* 18 The Cyber Range should allows trainees to (Select all that apply):

- Save and resume scenarios
- Save and resume the virtual machines of a scenario
- Record and replay events on the scenarios

* 19 The Cyber Range scenario should allows individual VM/Containers etc. to connect to the Internet to download and install packages (even temporarily):

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No
- Should be configurable for each scenario

* 20 The scenarios of the Cyber Range should be:

- Non-customisable
- eXperience API (xAPI) integration
- Sharable Content Object Reference Model (SCORM)
- No integration/ Don't care
- Other

21 Other (please specify):

* 22 The Cyber Range services and training should aligns with the following framework:

- NIST framework
- NICE framework
- MITRE ATT&CK
- MITRE CAPEC
- NSA/DHS National Centers for Academic Excellence Knowledge Units
- Allows alignment to custom framework
- Other

23 Other (please specify):

* 24 The Cyber Range can support assessments allowing trainers/educators to (more than one selection is possible):

- Schedule a cyber exercise on a particular date and time
- Individual / asynchronous training and exercises
- Set a password for an active/scheduled cyber exercise
- Monitor the participant's progress on a live cyber exercise
- Review actions of learners participating in a cyber exercise through record/replay features
- Facilitate feedback to learners by assigning them a mark and comments on their performance
- Other

25 Other (please specify):

* 26 The Cyber Range can support the following users with different roles (more than one selection is possible):

- Red – member can play the role of attacker, pentester, and ethical hackers
- Blue – member can play the role of a defensive team member that allows improving and learning about different attack techniques
- White - created for instructor, moderators and administrators; it allows content management, monitoring of the learners and overall evaluations
- Green – support and technical monitoring of the cyber range infrastructure
- Purple – ethical hacking aimed at increasing protection of skills
- Grey – reference, support, coordination, scoring, process and supervision

* 27 The Cyber Range should provide:

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Initial Support and Training
- Periodic Support and Training
- On-Call Support and Training
- On-Call Support to develop new scenarios and/or cyber exercise

* 28 The Cyber Range should host CTF events supporting:

- Single users
- Multiple users
- Red teams (simulated or live)
- Blue teams
- Live scoring and leader board

* 29 The Cyber Range should simulate/should have the capacity to run (Select all that apply):

- Real benign traffic

5

- Malicious traffic
- Collection of IoCs

* 30 The Cyber Range should support the Operational Technology (OT) in addition to Information Technology (IT) systems:

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No

* 31 The Cyber Range should allows users with sufficient permissions to:

- Create new scenarios
- Modify an existing scenario
- Clone existing scenarios
- Modify a live scenario
- Export existing scenario
- Import scenarios from a compatible source
- Map scenarios and labs to a competency framework
- Automatically discover a real network and (partially) reconstruct its emulation within a Cyber Range scenario
- Run multiple scenario instances in parallel

* 32 The Cyber Range should provide a catalogue of existing scenarios or labs:

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No

33 If yes, specify which scenarios should be available:

34 If yes, specify how many scenarios should be stored in the cyber range:

* 35 The Cyber Range should support scenarios to test single assets or combination of assets:

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes, with specific features such as test timelines, configuration of the Security Targets, traceability to security requirements, reporting, etc.
- Yes, without specific features
- No

* 36 The Cyber Range should provide an asset library of virtual templates to be used to create or customize scenarios:

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No

37 If Yes, the Asset Library:

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Can be further expanded
- Includes a variety of different assets licensed and/or opensource (include a list of the available assets)
- Each asset can be contextualised and configured on cyber range scenarios via scripting language (for example, Ansible)

* 38 Type of supported assessment for training scenarios:

- Automated or semi-automated trainee performance assessments
- Manual trainee performance assessment
- Reports generation
- Customisable questionnaire

* 39 In your view, what are the most significant obstacles to implement or participate in a Cyber Range?
(Please detail any technical, organizational, or operational challenges.)

Training and Development

* 40 What specific skills or competencies should employees receive throughout a Cyber Range-based training program? (Please list in order of priority.)

* 41 How do you believe success should be quantified in Cyber Range training exercises? (Select all that apply)

- Quantitative improvement in technical skills (please specify metrics if any)
- Enhanced incident response and decision-making speed
- Achievement of personalized training objectives
- Increased participant engagement and feedback ratings
- Other

42 Other (Please specify):

Collaboration and Information Sharing

*

7

43 Rate the importance of a Cyber Range in enabling cross-sector collaboration (e.g., with telecommunications, financial services) for cybersecurity in your sector.

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Very Important
- Somewhat Important
- Not Important

* 44 Would you be willing to share insights and outcomes from Cyber Range exercises with other stakeholders in your sector to foster a community of practice?

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

45 Maybe (Please specify conditions):

Feedback and Additional Comments

* 46 What additional features or capabilities would you recommend for a Cyber Range to be most effective for your sector? (Please provide specific examples or suggestions.)

* 47 Are there any existing models or practices from other sectors or industries that you believe could be beneficial to be integrated into your sector-specific Cyber Range?

Statistics: SecAwarenessTruss Cyber Security Training Requirements For Non-IT Professionals

How many years do you have in your current role?

		Answers	Ratio
Less than a year		9	8.26 %
1-3 years		28	25.69 %
4-6 years		12	11.01 %
7-10 years		10	9.17 %
More than 10 years		50	45.87 %
No Answer		0	0 %

■ Less than a year ■ 1-3 years
■ 4-6 years ■ 7-10 years
■ More than 10 years

What is the size of your organization?

		Answers	Ratio
Small (1-50 employees)		1	0.92 %
Medium (51-200 employees)		36	33.03 %
Large (201-500 employees)		2	1.83 %
Enterprise (501+ employees)		70	64.22 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Which sector does your organization operate in? (Please select the most relevant)

		Answers	Ratio
Energy		12	11.01 %
Healthcare		35	32.11 %
Maritime		18	16.51 %
Telecoms		21	19.27 %
Finance		3	2.75 %
Government		20	18.35 %
No Answer		0	0 %

How often does your organization update you on new cybersecurity threats and safety practices?

		Answers	Ratio
Every month		14	12.84 %
Every six months		23	21.1 %
Every year		13	11.93 %
Every two years		4	3.67 %
More than two years		4	3.67 %
Unsure/Don't know		51	46.79 %
No Answer		0	0 %

How would you rate your organization's current cybersecurity posture?

		Answers	Ratio
Very advanced - we are at the cutting edge of cybersecurity practices		8	7.34 %
Advanced - we have a strong cybersecurity framework in place		55	50.46 %
Moderate - we are doing okay but could improve		22	20.18 %
Basic - we are somewhat vulnerable and need to do more		6	5.5 %
Unsure/Don't know		18	16.51 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Does your organisation have a dedicated team or individual responsible for cybersecurity?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		80	73.39 %
No		7	6.42 %
Unsure/Don't know		22	20.18 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Have you ever experienced or witnessed a cybersecurity incident (e.g., data breach, malware attack) in your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		48	44.04 %
No		48	44.04 %
Unsure/Don't know		13	11.93 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Does your organization require regular password changes for work-related accounts and systems?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		75	68.81 %
No		28	25.69 %
Unsure/Don't know		6	5.5 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Does your organisation restrict the use of external devices (e.g., USB drives, personal smartphones) on work devices?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		37	33.94 %
No		60	55.05 %
Unsure/Don't know		12	11.01 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Does your organisation use anti-virus or anti-malware software on work devices?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		104	95.41 %
No		2	1.83 %
Unsure/Don't know		3	2.75 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Are you aware of what to do if you lose a work device (e.g., laptop, smartphone)?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		76	69.72 %
No		26	23.85 %
Unsure/Don't know		7	6.42 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Are you aware of the risks associated with using public Wi-Fi networks for work-related activities?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		97	88.99 %
No		8	7.34 %
Unsure/Don't know		4	3.67 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Has your organisation ever conducted a simulated phishing exercise to test employee awareness?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		25	22.94 %
No		49	44.95 %
Unsure/Don't know		35	32.11 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Do you know how frequently does your organisation back up critical data?

		Answers	Ratio
Every day		44	40.37 %
Every week		2	1.83 %
Every month		1	0.92 %
Every six months		0	0 %
Unsure/Don't know		62	56.88 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Statistics: SecAwarenessTruss Cyber Security Training Requirements For IT Professionals

Your Role in the Organization:

		Answers	Ratio
Executive Management		2	4.88 %
IT/Cybersecurity Professional		22	53.66 %
Operational Technology (OT) Professional		1	2.44 %
Research and Development		12	29.27 %
Other		4	9.76 %
No Answer		0	0 %

How many years have you been working in your current role?

		Answers	Ratio
Less than a year		5	12.2 %
1-3 years		8	19.51 %
4-6 years		4	9.76 %
7-10 years		5	12.2 %
More than 10 years		19	46.34 %
No Answer		0	0 %

What is the size of your organization?

		Answers	Ratio
Small (1-50 employees)		2	4.88 %
Medium (51-200 employees)		3	7.32 %
Large (201-500 employees)		3	7.32 %
Enterprise (501+ employees)		33	80.49 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Which sector does your organization operate in? (Please select the most relevant)

		Answers	Ratio
Energy		6	14.63 %
Telecommunications		5	12.2 %
Healthcare		23	56.1 %
Maritime		3	7.32 %
Government		1	2.44 %
Finance		0	0 %
Other		3	7.32 %
No Answer		0	0 %

What is your primary cybersecurity concern? (Select all that apply)

		Answers	Ratio
Protecting customer data		30	73.17 %
Ensuring system availability		36	87.8 %
Compliance with regulatory requirements		25	60.98 %
Preventing ransomware attacks		28	68.29 %
Safeguarding intellectual property		20	48.78 %
Employee training and awareness		29	70.73 %
Other		0	0 %
No Answer		0	0 %

How would you rate your organization's current cybersecurity posture?

		Answers	Ratio
Very advanced - we are at the cutting edge of cybersecurity practices		2	4.88 %
Advanced - we have a strong cybersecurity framework in place		30	73.17 %
Moderate - we are doing okay but could improve		6	14.63 %
Basic - we are somewhat vulnerable and need to do more		1	2.44 %
Unsure/Don't know		2	4.88 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Which of the below standards, regulations, and/or guidelines are you utilizing as part of your cybersecurity practices:

		Answers	Ratio
ISO/IEC 27001		8	19.51 %
ISO/IEC 27002		5	12.2 %
ISO/IEC 27005		2	4.88 %
ISO/IEC 27017		1	2.44 %
ISO/IEC 27018		1	2.44 %
ISO/IEC 27701		3	7.32 %
NIST SP 800-30		1	2.44 %
NIST SP 800-53		1	2.44 %
NIST's Cybersecurity Framework		2	4.88 %
IMO: Resolution MSC.428(98)		0	0 %
IMO: MSC-FAL.1/Circ.3		0	0 %
BIMCO		0	0 %
None		16	39.02 %
Don't know		16	39.02 %
Other		0	0 %
No Answer		0	0 %

How familiar are you with the concept and functionalities of Cyber Ranges?

		Answers	Ratio
Very Familiar		8	19.51 %
Somewhat Familiar		23	56.1 %
Not Familiar		10	24.39 %
No Answer		0	0 %

■ Very Familiar
 ■ Somewhat Familiar
 ■ Not Familiar

What are your primary objectives for utilizing a Cyber Range? (Select all that apply)

		Answers	Ratio
Training and enhancing cybersecurity skills		33	80.49 %
Testing system resilience to cyber-attacks		29	70.73 %
Conducting cybersecurity research and development		21	51.22 %
Simulating cyber incident response		25	60.98 %
Other		1	2.44 %
No Answer		0	0 %

■ Training and enhancing cybersecur...
 ■ Testing system resilience to cybe...
 ■ Conducting cybersecurity research...
 ■ Simulating cyber incident respons...
 ■ Other

Which features do you consider crucial for a Cyber Range? (Select all that apply)

		Answers	Ratio
Simulation of specialised/OT systems (e.g., SCADA)		15	36.59 %
Capability to simulate specific types of cyber threats (e.g., ransomware, APTs)		31	75.61 %
Integration with existing IT/OT infrastructure for realistic testing		24	58.54 %
Support for collaborative exercises with other organizations		21	51.22 %
Automated feedback and performance evaluation tools		25	60.98 %
Compliance testing with regulatory standards (e.g., NIS2, NIST SP800-82, ISA/IEC 62443, GDPR)		21	51.22 %
Other		0	0 %
No Answer		0	0 %

What would be the ideal location of a Cyber Range for you:

		Answers	Ratio
On premise		20	48.78 %
Cloud- based (remote)		3	7.32 %
Hybrid (blend of on premise and cloud- based)		18	43.9 %
Mobile and portable solution		0	0 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range should support:

		Answers	Ratio
Limited number of users for a limited time period		3	7.32 %
Limited number of users for an unlimited time period		6	14.63 %
Unlimited number of users for a limited time period		5	12.2 %
Unlimited number of users for an unlimited time period		19	46.34 %
Interoperability with remote orchestrators, scenarios		13	31.71 %
Possibility to federate with other scenarios		10	24.39 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range should allows trainees to (Select all that apply):

		Answers	Ratio
Save and resume scenarios		21	51.22 %
Save and resume the virtual machines of a scenario		32	78.05 %
Record and replay events on the scenarios		18	43.9 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range scenario should allows individual VM/Containers etc. to connect to the Internet to download and install packages (even temporarily):

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		16	39.02 %
No		2	4.88 %
Should be configurable for each scenario		23	56.1 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The scenarios of the Cyber Range should be:

		Answers	Ratio
Non-customisable		2	4.88 %
eXperience API (xAPI) integration		29	70.73 %
Sharable Content Object Reference Model (SCORM)		15	36.59 %
No integration/ Don't care		6	14.63 %
Other		1	2.44 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range services and training should aligns with the following framework:

		Answers	Ratio
NIST framework		19	46.34 %
NICE framework		6	14.63 %
MITRE ATT&CK		7	17.07 %
MITRE CAPEC		3	7.32 %
NSA/DHS National Centers for Academic Excellence Knowledge Units		5	12.2 %
Allows alignment to custom framework		20	48.78 %
Other		8	19.51 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range can support assessments allowing trainers/educators to (more than one selection is possible):

		Answers	Ratio
Schedule a cyber exercise on a particular date and time		26	63.41 %
Individual / asynchronous training and exercises		26	63.41 %
Set a password for an active/scheduled cyber exercise		15	36.59 %
Monitor the participant's progress on a live cyber exercise		29	70.73 %
Review actions of learners participating in a cyber exercise through record/replay features		22	53.66 %
Facilitate feedback to learners by assigning them a mark and comments on their performance		21	51.22 %
Other		0	0 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range can support the following users with different roles (more than one selection is possible):

		Answers	Ratio
Red – member can play the role of attacker, pentester, and ethical hackers		33	80.49 %
Blue – member can play the role of a defensive team member that allows improving and learning about different attack techniques		38	92.68 %
White - created for instructor, moderators and administrators; it allows content management, monitoring of the learners and overall evaluations		26	63.41 %
Green – support and technical monitoring of the cyber range infrastructure		20	48.78 %
Purple – ethical hacking aimed at increasing protection of skills		22	53.66 %
Grey – reference, support, coordination, scoring, process and supervision		22	53.66 %
No Answer		0	0 %

- Red – member can play the role of...
- Blue – member can play the role o...
- White - created for instructor, m...
- Green – support and technical mon...
- Purple – ethical hacking aimed at...
- Grey – reference, support, coordi...

The Cyber Range should provide:

		Answers	Ratio
Initial Support and Training		3	7.32 %
Periodic Support and Training		12	29.27 %
On-Call Support and Training		16	39.02 %
On-Call Support to develop new scenarios and/or cyber exercise		10	24.39 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range should host CTF events supporting:

		Answers	Ratio
Single users	<div style="width: 4px; height: 10px; background-color: blue;"></div>	4	9.76 %
Multiple users	<div style="width: 37px; height: 10px; background-color: blue;"></div>	37	90.24 %
Red teams (simulated or live)	<div style="width: 13px; height: 10px; background-color: blue;"></div>	13	31.71 %
Blue teams	<div style="width: 12px; height: 10px; background-color: blue;"></div>	12	29.27 %
Live scoring and leader board	<div style="width: 14px; height: 10px; background-color: blue;"></div>	14	34.15 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range should simulate/should have the capacity to run (Select all that apply):

		Answers	Ratio
Real benign traffic	<div style="width: 33px; height: 10px; background-color: blue;"></div>	33	80.49 %
Malicious traffic	<div style="width: 33px; height: 10px; background-color: blue;"></div>	33	80.49 %
Collection of IoCs	<div style="width: 30px; height: 10px; background-color: blue;"></div>	30	73.17 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range should support the Operational Technology (OT) in addition to Information Technology (IT) systems:

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		30	73.17 %
No		11	26.83 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range should allows users with sufficient permissions to:

		Answers	Ratio
Create new scenarios		26	63.41 %
Modify an existing scenario		25	60.98 %
Clone existing scenarios		18	43.9 %
Modify a live scenario		23	56.1 %
Export existing scenario		19	46.34 %
Import scenarios from a compatible source		27	65.85 %
Map scenarios and labs to a competency framework		21	51.22 %
Automatically discover a real network and (partially) reconstruct its emulation within a Cyber Range scenario		16	39.02 %
Run multiple scenario instances in parallel		20	48.78 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range should provide a catalogue of existing scenarios or labs:

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		18	43.9 %
No		23	56.1 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range should support scenarios to test single assets or combination of assets:

		Answers	Ratio
Yes, with specific features such as test timelines, configuration of the Security Targets, traceability to security requirements, reporting, etc.		20	48.78 %
Yes, without specific features		19	46.34 %
No		2	4.88 %
No Answer		0	0 %

The Cyber Range should provide an asset library of virtual templates to be used to create or customize scenarios:

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		35	85.37 %
No		6	14.63 %
No Answer		0	0 %

If Yes, the Asset Library:

		Answers	Ratio
Can be further expanded		15	36.59 %
Includes a variety of different assets licensed and /or opensource (include a list of the available assets)		16	39.02 %
Each asset can be contextualised and configured on cyber range scenarios via scripting language (for example, Ansible)		4	9.76 %
No Answer		6	14.63 %

Type of supported assessment for training scenarios:

		Answers	Ratio
Automated or semi-automated trainee performance assessments		30	73.17 %
Manual trainee performance assessment		18	43.9 %
Reports generation		28	68.29 %
Customisable questionnaire		10	24.39 %
No Answer		0	0 %

How do you believe success should be quantified in Cyber Range training exercises? (Select all that apply)

		Answers	Ratio
Quantitative improvement in technical skills (please specify metrics if any)		26	63.41 %
Enhanced incident response and decision-making speed		27	65.85 %
Achievement of personalized training objectives		24	58.54 %
Increased participant engagement and feedback ratings		21	51.22 %
Other		0	0 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Rate the importance of a Cyber Range in enabling cross-sector collaboration (e.g., with telecommunications, financial services) for cybersecurity in your sector.

		Answers	Ratio
Very Important		20	48.78 %
Somewhat Important		20	48.78 %
Not Important		1	2.44 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Would you be willing to share insights and outcomes from Cyber Range exercises with other stakeholders in your sector to foster a community of practice?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		17	41.46 %
No		10	24.39 %
Maybe		14	34.15 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Funded by the
European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No Project 101128049